

Transformer-based SHM of Semiconductor Probe Cards: Unifying Optimal Sensor Placement and Missing-Data Imputation for Reliable Online Monitoring

Mehdi Bejani^{1,2}, Marco Mauri², Stefano Mariani¹

¹*Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering*

Politecnico di Milano

Milan, Italy

mehdi.bejani@polimi.it

²*Technoprobe*

Cernusco Lombardone, Italy

Abstract—Structural health monitoring of semiconductor probe cards is essential to prevent downtime and yield loss during wafer-level testing. However, the reliability of monitoring systems is frequently compromised by sensor data loss during operation and the challenge of identifying the most informative sensor locations. This work proposes a unified deep learning framework that merges optimal sensor placement with advanced missing data imputation techniques. We employ a hybrid convolutional neural network-Transformer architecture to classify failure modes, including cracks and loose screws, based on frequency response functions, and utilize attention weights to identify optimal sensor configurations. To address data completeness, we integrate the self-attention-based imputation for time series model. We evaluate the robustness of our framework by comparing this imputation method against k-nearest neighbors imputation and complete data as a baseline. Results demonstrate that while standard k-nearest neighbors imputation causes a drastic drop in diagnostic balanced accuracy (from 96.2% to 64.7%) and renders rare failure modes nearly undetectable (19.5% recall), the proposed self-attention-based approach significantly recovers performance (74.3% balanced accuracy, 40.0% recall). Furthermore, the self-attention-based method preserves the physical hierarchy of sensor importance, ensuring reliable optimal sensor placement even in the presence of data loss.

Index Terms—Structural Health Monitoring, Optimal Sensor Placement, Deep Learning, Transformer, Probe Card, Missing Data Imputation, SAITS

I. INTRODUCTION

In the semiconductor manufacturing industry, the probe card (PC) serves as the critical electromechanical interface between the automated test equipment (ATE) and the silicon wafer [1]. As integrated circuits continue to shrink in accordance with Moore’s Law, the mechanical complexity of PCs has increased, amplifying the effects of failure modes such as ceramic cracks, screw loosening, and thermal misalignment. These failures can lead to erroneous test results, false rejections of functional dies, and significant economic losses due to unscheduled downtime [1]. The structural complexity and the specific

failure modes addressed in this study—specifically mechanical failures in the probe head and ceramics—are illustrated in Fig. 1.

Traditional methodologies employed for the detection of PC failures rely on manual visual inspections or electrical tests, which may only succeed in identifying problems once a significant level of degradation has already occurred. Furthermore, such methods often necessitate the interruption of the testing process, leading to inefficiencies in the production workflow. In practice, maintenance engineers frequently depend on their accumulated domain-specific knowledge and engage in time-consuming trial-and-error procedures to diagnose faults and undertake troubleshooting efforts [1], [2].

To mitigate these risks, structural health monitoring (SHM) frameworks utilizing vibration and acoustic sensors have emerged as a promising solution for predictive maintenance [3]. However, deploying robust SHM in an industrial setting faces two primary challenges:

- 1) **The optimal sensor placement (OSP) problem:** PCs have strict spatial constraints, requiring the identification of a minimal set of sensors that maximizes diagnostic information [4], [5].
- 2) **The missing data problem:** Real-time sensor networks in industrial internet of things (IoT) environments are prone to data loss due to transmission errors, sensor malfunctions, or environmental interference [6]. Missing data severely compromises the performance of deep learning (DL) classifiers and destabilizes OSP algorithms, leading to unreliable monitoring [7], [8].

This paper addresses these challenges by unifying OSP and imputation into a single resilient framework. We build upon previous work that utilized Transformer attention mechanisms for interpretable OSP [4] and extend it by integrating the self-attention-based imputation for time series (SAITS) model [8], [9]. We demonstrate that advanced imputation is not merely

a data-cleaning step but a prerequisite for maintaining the integrity of the SHM system.

Fig. 1. Structure of the probe card and associated failure modes for each component. [4].

A. Key Contributions

This paper provides the following contributions:

- **Unified Framework:** Integration of the OSP with advanced missing data imputation in a single coherent methodology
- **Comprehensive Evaluation:** Rigorous comparison of imputation methods (SAITS vs. k-nearest neighbors) across multiple performance dimensions
- **Physical Validation:** Demonstration that SAITS preserves the physical hierarchy of sensor importance, critical for reliable OSP
- **Practical Insights:** Analysis of performance degradation under realistic missing data scenarios, with specific focus on rare failure mode detection

II. RELATED WORK

As Electrical Wafer Sort diagnostics have grown more complex, AI methods have been applied to semiconductor equipment and PC related analytics, including Bayesian models and neural architectures for fault diagnosis [10], [11], support vector machine based anomaly detection [12], autoencoder/event-log frameworks for early fault detection [13], and learning-based approaches for lifetime prediction and replacement optimization [14]. These directions establish the industrial relevance of data-driven monitoring but do not by themselves solve the continuous, vibration-based monitoring problem posed by mechanical PC degradations.

SHM approaches address this limitation by using embedded sensing to detect structural changes through dynamic response features. For PCs, frequency response functions (FRFs) are particularly valuable because they respond sensitively to structural damage via changes in resonant frequencies, damping behavior, and mode shapes [15], [16], supporting non-destructive assessment through vibration/acoustic monitoring.

OSP has a long tradition in SHM, with classical methods providing principled criteria for selecting measurement locations. Major families include Fisher information matrix based-frameworks [17], [18], entropy-based methods [19], [20], modal assurance criterion-based approaches targeting

independent mode-shape capture [21], [22], and value of information frameworks formalizing sensing-cost vs diagnostic-benefit trade-offs [23], [24]. While rigorous, these approaches often require explicit objective definition, modal parameter availability, and iterative optimization, which can become expensive and less flexible when scaling to high-dimensional FRF datasets and complex multi-sensor interactions.

DL has become central in SHM because it can learn discriminative representations directly from raw sensor inputs, reducing dependence on handcrafted features and domain-specific preprocessing [25]–[27]. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have succeeded in vibration-based machinery diagnosis [3], acoustic anomaly detection [28], and FRF-based damage identification [15]. Yet CNNs alone are not designed to model global inter-sensor dependencies, motivating hybrid approaches and attention mechanisms to capture relationships across sensors [29].

Transformer networks—originally developed for language modeling—enable self-attention to weight parts of the input dynamically and have gained traction for multivariate time-series tasks [30]. In PC SHM, attention is particularly appealing because it supports interpretability: attention weights can be examined to infer which sensors most influence classification, thereby enabling data-driven OSP without explicit combinatorial search [4], [29].

Missing values are pervasive in industrial IoT and SHM due to device malfunctions, communication loss, and environmental interference [7], [31]. Basic statistical imputations (mean/median/mode) ignore temporal dependence and distort signal variance [32]. Advanced interpolation methods (e.g., Piecewise Cubic Hermite Interpolating Polynomial [33]) often fail for longer gaps [6], [34]. Classical ML methods such as k-nearest neighbors (KNN) [32] and random forest [35] exploit similarity structure, while multivariate imputation by chained equations [36] leverage multivariate correlations.

DL approaches better address long-range temporal structure. Recurrent neural network variants, such as long short-term memory networks and gated recurrent units [31], learn sequential representations. Transformer-based imputers [34], [37] offer parallelizable self-attention. SAITS [9] combines masked self-attention blocks with joint optimization designed to preserve temporal fidelity and spectral characteristics—key for high-frequency probe-card sensing signals.

III. METHODOLOGY

The proposed framework consists of three integrated modules: (1) A digital shadow for data generation, (2) A missing data imputation module (comparing KNN and SAITS), and (3) A Transformer-based classifier that performs both failure diagnosis and OSP via attention analysis. The overall architecture is illustrated in Fig. 2.

A. Problem Formulation

Based on historical failure data analysis, this study focuses on mechanical failures that are both critical and challenging to detect:

Fig. 2. Overall framework.

Cracks in Probe Card Plates: Cracks pose critical risks to mechanical integrity and probe tip alignment. Finite element (FE) analyses using ANSYS Mechanical R2 2024 [38] revealed that cracks significantly alter the FRF, particularly within the 400–4000 Hz band (audible spectrum), supporting the use of microphones to capture acoustic signatures.

Loosening of Screws: The probe head integrity is maintained by screws at specific locations (Fig. 3). Variations in screw torque could lead to tip misalignment. FE simulations confirmed that minor torque deviations produce distinguishable spectral changes in FRFs.

Fig. 3. Numbering scheme for the 21 screws joining the probe head lower frame (left) to the housing (right) [4].

B. Digital Shadow and Data Generation

We utilized a FE digital shadow simulating dynamic response under various health states: Baseline (healthy, 125 scenarios after physics-informed expansion), loose screws (torque variations, 2,625 scenarios), and cracks (structural fissures, 1,000 scenarios). Virtual sensors were placed at 28 candidate locations (Fig. 4). FRFs were extracted for each scenario, capturing the spectral signature of the mechanical state [39].

Fig. 4. Representation of the 28 locations on the lower side (left) and upper side (right) of the probe head, where FRFs were extracted [4].

C. Physics-Informed Scenario Expansion

To address dataset imbalance and provide more training data, we employed physics-informed scenario expansion varying:

Material Properties: Controlled variation on Young’s modulus and density of silicon nitride (SiN) and metal alloy (MeAl) components. Five distinct cases: nominal, maximum properties, minimum properties, and two mixed cases. SiN exhibits $\pm 5\%$ density and $\pm 10\%$ Young’s modulus variation; MeAl shows $\pm 2\%$ density and $\pm 5\%$ Young’s modulus variation.

Environmental Conditions: Five temperatures (25°C, 100°C, 150°C, 200°C, 250°C) accounting for thermal effects.

Loading Conditions: Five distributed load magnitudes (0.1 MPa, 0.5 MPa, 1 MPa, 1.5 MPa, 2 MPa) representing different operational scenarios.

Combining all cases, 125 variant conditions were generated per initial scenario, increasing the dataset to 3,750 samples while maintaining physical realism.

D. Missing Data Imputation

K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN): A traditional ML approach imputing missing values based on similarity to $k = 5$ nearest complete samples [8], weighting contributions by inverse distance.

SAITS (Proposed): We employ the Self-Attention-based Imputation for Time Series model [9]. SAITS utilizes diagonally-masked self-attention (DMSA) blocks to capture long-range temporal dependencies and cross-feature correlations. The architecture consists of two parallel DMSA blocks processing input after linear projection and positional encoding.

Based on systematic hyperparameter optimization [8], we adopted: 3 layers per DMSA block, embedding dimension 256, learning rate 0.001, training up to 150 epochs with early stopping (patience=50), 4 attention heads, dropout 0.05, Adam optimizer with weight decay 1×10^{-5} . Best model selected from epoch 83 based on validation MSE of 0.2354.

E. Transformer-based Classification and OSP

The reconstructed data feeds into a hybrid CNN-Transformer model (TransformerSHM), as illustrated in Fig. 5).

Sensor Encoder: 1D CNN layers extract local spectral features. The architecture employs four sequential convolutional layers (32→64→128→128), each with batch normalization, ReLU activation, and max pooling. Adaptive average pooling reduces sequences to fixed-length embedding vectors of dimension 128.

Transformer Integration: Self-attention mechanisms model global dependencies between sensors. The module implements multi-layer Transformer encoder with two encoder layers, each incorporating multi-head self-attention with four attention heads.

Classification & OSP: An attention-based classification head predicts the health state (Baseline, Loose Screw, Crack). Attention weights produced by the Transformer encoder are extracted to quantify sensor importance for OSP [4].

The model was trained using cross-entropy loss with class weights and L1 regularization on final classification attention weights ($\lambda = 1 \times 10^{-4}$) to encourage sparsity.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Dataset Characteristics

The dataset consists of 3,750 samples split into training (80%), validation (10%), and testing (10%). Each sample comprises data from 28 sensors with 150 frequency points, resulting in input dimensions of (Batch, 28, 150).

B. Missing Data Simulation

We artificially introduced missing data blocks into the test set using a Missing Completely at Random (MCAR) mechanism with 10% missing rate and block length of 5 consecutive time steps. This models brief sensor dropouts commonly observed in industrial IoT environments.

C. Experimental Scenarios and Evaluation

We evaluate three scenarios: (1) clean data (baseline), (2) KNN imputation, (3) SAITS imputation.

Performance is evaluated using classification metrics (accuracy, balanced accuracy, class-specific precision/recall/F1-score, ROC AUC), time-domain imputation metrics (mean absolute error (MAE), mean relative error (MRE), root mean square error (RMSE), similarity coefficient (Sim), fraction of standard deviation (FSD), and frequency-domain metrics ($RMSE_F$, $RMSE_{F_{Low}}$, $RMSE_{F_{High}}$).

Training utilized 10-fold stratified cross-validation repeated three times. Within each fold, an ensemble of ten models was

Fig. 5. Transformer SHM model scheme [4].

trained with different random seeds, totaling 30 independent models. Training used early stopping (30-epoch patience), learning rate reduction on plateau, and Adam optimizer with initial learning rate 1×10^{-4} .

V. RESULTS

A. SAITS Training Performance

The SAITS model demonstrated rapid convergence. The best performing model was obtained at epoch 83 (validation MSE: 0.2354, training MAE: 0.0770). Training terminated at epoch 113 due to early stopping. Final metrics: training MAE 0.0705, validation MSE 0.2527. Training required approximately 5 minutes on NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 hardware.

B. Imputation Quality Assessment

Table I summarizes imputation performance averaged across all 28 sensors with 10% missing rate.

TABLE I
COMPARATIVE IMPUTATION PERFORMANCE

Metric	Original	KNN	SAITS
MAE	0.00	273.86	188.70
MRE	0.00	0.68	1.76
RMSE	0.00	401.90	284.56
Sim	1.00	0.77	0.90
FSD	0.00	0.87	0.56
RMSE _F	0.00	1114.47	801.23
RMSE _{F_{Low}}	0.00	2209.67	1600.27
RMSE _{F_{High}}	0.00	601.81	476.84

SAITS achieves superior reconstruction quality. SAITS reduces MAE by 31.1% (188.70 vs 273.86) and achieves similarity coefficient of 0.90 (vs 0.77 for KNN). In the frequency domain, SAITS reduces overall RMSE_F by 28.1% (801.23 vs 1114.47), critical for distinguishing mechanical failure modes in the 400–4000 Hz range. FSD metric shows SAITS achieves 0.56 vs KNN’s 0.87, indicating SAITS-reconstructed signals have scale characteristics closer to original data.

C. Classification Performance

Table II presents classification metrics aggregated across all validation folds.

TABLE II
CLASSIFICATION PERFORMANCE COMPARISON

Metric	Original	KNN	SAITS
Accuracy	97.88%	86.81%	90.98%
Balanced Acc.	96.16%	64.73%	74.31%
ROC AUC	0.9829	0.9202	0.9601

In the original (clean) scenario, the model achieves a theoretical upper bound of 97.9% accuracy and a balanced accuracy of 96.16%, confirming that the TransformerSHM architecture is highly effective when data is complete.

However, under KNN Imputation, while overall accuracy remains seemingly high (86.8%), the balanced accuracy collapses to 64.73%. This drastic drop indicates that simple interpolation biases the model toward majority classes, failing to detect specific failure modes. The ROC AUC also degrades significantly to 0.9202.

The proposed SAITS framework significantly recovers the system fidelity, restoring balanced accuracy to 74.31% and ROC AUC to 0.9601. This represents a substantial improvement over KNN, recovering approximately 30% of the performance lost due to missing data

D. Class-Wise Performance

Table III examines class-wise performance.

The breakdown reveals that class 0 is the primary casualty of poor imputation. With KNN, the recall for class 0 is only 19.5%, meaning the system misses 4 out of 5 occurrences of this state. The confusion matrix analysis confirmed that 250 samples of class 0 were misclassified as class 2, indicating

TABLE III
CLASS-WISE PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Class	Method	Prec.	Recall	F1
class 0	Original	0.825	0.937	0.871
	KNN	0.296	0.195	0.221
	SAITS	0.510	0.400	0.428
class 1	Original	0.989	0.988	0.987
	KNN	0.945	0.913	0.928
	SAITS	0.967	0.943	0.955
class 2	Original	0.952	0.959	0.956
	KNN	0.745	0.834	0.784
	SAITS	0.819	0.887	0.850

that KNN-imputed data loses the subtle spectral signatures necessary to distinguish baseline from incipient failure states.

SAITS doubles the recall of this hard class to 40.0% and improves precision to 51.0%, effectively rescuing the system’s ability to monitor rare or subtle states. While this is still significantly below the Original performance (93.7% recall), it represents a crucial improvement that could mean the difference between detecting an emerging failure early or missing it entirely.

For class 1 and class 2, both imputation methods maintain relatively strong performance, with SAITS consistently outperforming KNN. This suggests that majority classes are more robust to imputation errors, but the detection of critical minority failure modes requires advanced imputation techniques.

E. Model Robustness

Fig. 6 shows accuracy distribution across 30 independent models.

Fig. 6. Accuracy distribution across 30 models.

The clean data scenario shows high stability with a very narrow interquartile range (IQR), with median accuracy above 99%. KNN imputation introduces significant instability, with accuracy fluctuating widely between 87% and 96%, rendering the system unpredictable across different data folds. This high variance suggests that KNN performance is highly sensitive to the specific patterns present in the training data.

SAITS reduces this variance significantly, tightening the IQR and raising the median accuracy to approximately 96%.

The distribution is much more concentrated, with fewer outliers, demonstrating that the advanced imputation restores the consistency of the classifier across different data partitions.

This stability is crucial for industrial deployment, where the SHM system must maintain reliable performance across varying operating conditions, seasonal changes, and evolving failure patterns.

F. Impact on Optimal Sensor Placement

Fig. 7 shows sensor importance weights extracted from Transformer attention mechanism.

Original Hierarchy: The clean data produces a sharp, distinct hierarchy where sensors 16, 15, and 14 are dominant (attention weights > 0.08), followed by sensors 7 and 9 (weights ~ 0.05). This physical cluster likely corresponds to critical stress concentration points near screw attachment locations and ceramic plate interfaces.

KNN Distortion: Under KNN imputation, this hierarchy is severely flattened. The distinction between the “best” sensors (14–16) and “average” sensors blurs significantly, with peak attention weights reduced to ~ 0.06 . Moreover, sensor 9 becomes disproportionately prominent relative to its importance in the original data. This “flattening” would lead to suboptimal sensor selection—engineers might mistakenly deploy sensors at less informative locations or deploy more sensors than necessary to compensate for reduced discrimination.

SAITS Recovery: SAITS faithfully reconstructs the original profile. The dominant peak at sensors 14, 15, and 16 is clearly recovered (weights ~ 0.075 – 0.08), closely matching the ground truth. The secondary importance of Sensors 7 and 9 is also preserved. This confirms that SAITS preserves the physical signal characteristics required for stable OSP.

The preservation of sensor importance hierarchy has critical practical implications:

- 1) **Deployment Efficiency:** Correct identification of the top 3–5 sensors allows for minimal sensor deployment while maintaining diagnostic capability
- 2) **Cost Reduction:** Fewer sensors mean lower hardware costs, reduced data transmission requirements, and simplified maintenance
- 3) **Physical Validation:** The fact that SAITS-identified sensors align with structural engineering expectations (near stress concentrations) provides confidence in the approach

VI. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that SAITS-based imputation successfully enables reliable failure classification despite missing sensor data. Three key findings emerge:

Superior Signal Reconstruction: SAITS significantly outperforms KNN with 31.1% lower MAE, 13 percentage points higher similarity, and 28.1% lower frequency-domain errors. This preserves the 400–4000 Hz spectral signatures that distinguish cracks from loose screws.

Enhanced Diagnostic Capability: The superior reconstruction translates to measurably better diagnostic capability.

Fig. 7. Sensor importance weights for: (a) Original (distinct hierarchy); (b) KNN (distorted profile); (c) SAITS (reconstructed hierarchy).

While KNN imputation causes balanced accuracy to collapse to 64.73%, SAITS recovers performance to 74.31%—representing 30% recovery of performance lost to missing data.

Critical for Rare Failure Detection: SAITS doubles recall for the challenging minority class from 19.5% to 40.0%. KNN acts as a low-pass filter, smoothing over distinct high-frequency spectral signatures required to identify subtle faults. A system using KNN might report seemingly acceptable overall accuracy (86.8%), masking the fact that it has lost ability to detect critical early-stage failures.

The framework demonstrates that imputation is inextricably linked to OSP. Poor imputation flattens sensor importance hierarchy, leading to suboptimal placement decisions. SAITS preserves the physical hierarchy, with attention weights correctly identifying Sensors 14–16 as most critical. This preservation has critical practical implications: correct identification of the top 3–5 sensors allows for minimal sensor deployment while maintaining diagnostic capability, reducing hardware costs, data transmission requirements, and simplified maintenance.

Limitations include simulation-based validation (physical hardware validation needed), MCAR assumption (real sensor failures may exhibit other patterns), and point estimates without uncertainty quantification. Future work includes real-time edge deployment optimization, multi-modal fusion (temperature sensors, electrical test metrics), transfer learning across PC designs, enhanced explainable AI for maintenance engineer

interpretation, and active sensor selection to minimize power consumption.

This approach provides a deployable path toward robust, data-efficient monitoring of complex semiconductor equipment. By unifying imputation and OSP in a single framework, we enable SHM systems that are both effective and resilient to real-world data quality challenges. The demonstrated framework has broader applicability beyond PCs, extending to any industrial IoT scenario where sensor reliability is uncertain and spatial constraints limit sensor deployment.

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